

Prediction of Diabetes Using Data Science Technique

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Abstract

Diabetes is a chronic (long-lasting) health condition that affects how your body turns food into energy. Most of the food you eat is broken down into sugar (also called glucose) and released into your bloodstream. When your blood sugar goes up, it signals your pancreas to release insulin. Diabetes should not be ignored if ignored then diabetes may cause some major issues in a person like heart related problems, kidney problem, blood pressure, eye damage and it can also effect the other organs of human body. So Early prediction of diabetes using various efficient machine learning methods can helps people to prevent the diabetes and to get the treatment earlier. Nowadays machine learning is applied to healthcare system where there is a chance of predicting the disease early. The main necessity of Artificial intelligence is data. In this we have proposed a diabetes prediction model for better classification of diabetes which includes few external factors responsible for diabetes along with regular factors loke glucose, age and BMI, etc. The past dataset is collected and that dataset is used to build a machine learning model. The necessary pre-processing techniques are applied like univariate analysis and bivariate analysis are implemented. The data is visualized for better understanding of the features and based on that a classification model is built by using machine learning algorithm like Decision tree, Support vector, Random Forest, Support vector etc and this comparison of algorithms are done based on their performance metrics like accuracy, F1 score recall etc. we explore various machine learning algorithms which will help in early prediction of this disease.

Introduction

Diabetes is noxious disease in the world. Diabetes caused because of obesity or high blood glucose level, and so forth. It affects the hormone insulin, resulting in abnormal metabolism of crabs and improves level of sugar in the blood. Diabetes occurs when body does not make enough insulin. According to (WHO) World Health Organization about 422 million people suffering from diabetes particularly from low- or idle-income countries. And this couldbe increased to 490 billion up to the year of 2030. However, prevalence of diabetes is found among various Countries like Canada, China, and India etc. Population of India is now more than 100 million so the actual number of diabetics in India is 40 million. Diabetes is major cause of death in the world. Diabetes is a disease which reduces the body's capability to produce insulin. In other words, the body can not retaliate to the hormone insulin production. This results in anomalous metabolism of carbohydrates and increased blood glucose levels. Early prediction of disease like diabetes can be controlled andsave the human life. The most explored area is the healthcare system which uses modern computing techniques is in healthcare research. As mentioned above the researchers in the related fields are already working with the healthcare organization to come up with more technology ready systems. Multiple opportunities for healthcare are created because machine learning

models have potential for advanced predictive analytics. There are already existing models in machine learning which can predict the chronic illness like heart disorder, infections and intestinal diseases. For this we apply various Machine Learning classification and ensemble Techniques to predict diabetes. Machine Learning Is a method that is used to train computers or machines explicitly. Various Machine Learning Techniques provide efficient result to collect Knowledge by building various classification and ensemble models from collected dataset. Such collected data can be useful to predict diabetes. Various techniques of Machine Learning can capable to do prediction, however it's tough to choose best Technique. Thus, for this purpose we apply popular classification and ensemble methods on dataset for prediction.

Data Science:

Data science is an interdisciplinary field that uses scientific methods, processes, algorithms and systems to extract knowledge and insights from structured and unstructured data, and apply knowledge and actionable insights from data across a broad range of application domains. The term "data science" has been traced back to 1974, when Peter Naur proposed it as an alternative name for computer science. In 1996, the International Federation of Classification Societies became the first conference to specifically feature data science as a topic. However, the definition was still influ.

The term “data science” was first coined in 2008 by D.J. Patil, and Jeff Hammerbacher, the pioneer leads of data and analytics efforts at LinkedIn and Facebook. In less than a decade, it has become one of the hottest and most trending professions in the market.

Machine learning:

Machine learning is to predict the future from past data. Machine learning(ML) is a type of artificial intelligence (AI) that provides computers with the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed. Machine learning focuses on the development of Computer Programs that can change when exposed to new data and the basics of Machine Learning, implementation of a simple machine learning algorithm using python. Process of training

Analyses Trains

Proposed System

The proposed method is to build a machine learning model for predicting Diabetes. The process carries from data collection where the past data related to Diabetes are collected. Data mining is a commonly used technique for processing enormous data in the healthcare domain. The Diabetes if found before proper treatment can save lives. Machine learning is now applied and mostly used in health care where it reduces the manual effort and better model makes error less which leads in saving the life. The data analysis is done on the dataset proper variable

Architecture of proposed model

Environmental Requirements:

1. Software Requirements: Operating System
2. Windows Tool: Anaconda with Jupyter Notebook 2.

Hardware requirements: Processor: Pentium IV/III
 Hard disk: minimum 80 GB RAM: minimum 2 GB

and prediction involves use of specialized algorithms. It feed the training data to an algorithm, and the algorithm uses this training data to give predictions on a new test data. Machine learning can be roughly separated in to three categories. There are supervised learning, unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning program is both given the input data and the corresponding labelling to learn data has to be labelled by a human being beforehand. Unsupervised learning is no labels. It provided to the learning algorithm. This algorithm has to figure out the clustering of the input data. Finally, Reinforcement learning dynamically interacts with its environment and it receives positive or negative feedback to improve its performance.

identification done that is both the dependent variables and independent variables are found. Then proper machine learning algorithm are applied on the dataset where the pattern of data is learnt. After applying different algorithms, a better algorithm is used for the prediction of outcome.

Advantages:

1. Chance of error rate is very less.
2. Time and Money saving.
3. Accuracy will be more as we are comparing with 4-5 types of algorithms

System Architecture:

False Positives (FP): A person who will pay predicted as defaulter. When actual class is no and predicted class is yes. E.g., if actual class says this passenger did not survive but predicted class tells you that this passenger will survive.

False Negatives (FN): A person who default predicted as payer. When actual class is yes but predicted class is no. E.g., if actual class value indicates that this passenger survived and predicted class tells you that passenger will die

True Positives (TP): A person who will not pay predicted as defaulter. These are the correctly predicted positive values which means that the value of actual class is yes and the value of predicted class is also yes. E.g., if actual class value indicates that this passenger survived and predicted class tells you the same thing.

True Negatives (TN): A person who default predicted as payer. These are the correctly predicted negative values which means that the value of actual class is no and value of predicted class is also no. E.g., if actual class says this passenger did not survive and predicted class tells you the same thing.

Comparing Algorithm with prediction in the form of best accuracy result:

It is important to compare the performance of multiple different machine learning algorithms consistently and it will discover to create a test harness to compare multiple different machine learning algorithms in Python with scikit-learn. It can use this test harness as a template on your own machine learning problems and add more and different algorithms to compare. Each model will have different performance characteristics. Using resampling methods like cross validation, you can get an estimate for how accurate each model may be on unseen data. It needs to be able to use these estimates to choose one or two best models from the suite of models that you have created. When have a new dataset, it is a good idea to visualize the data using different techniques in order to look at the data from different perspectives. The same idea applies to model selection. You should use a number of different ways of looking at the estimated accuracy of your machine learning algorithms in order to choose the one or two to finalize. In the next section you will discover exactly how you can do that in Python with scikit-learn. The key to a fair comparison of machine learning algorithms is ensuring that each algorithm is evaluated in the same way on the same data and it can achieve this

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FP})$$

by forcing each algorithm to be evaluated on a consistent test harness.

In the example below 4 different algorithms are compared:

- Logistic Regression
- Decision Tree
- Random Forest
- Support Vector Machine

The K-fold cross validation procedure is used to evaluate each algorithm, importantly configured with the same random seed to ensure that the same splits to the training data are performed and that each algorithm is evaluated in precisely the same way. Before that comparing algorithm, building a Machine Learning Model using install Scikit-Learn libraries. In this library package have to done pre-processing, linear model with logistic regression method, cross validating by K Fold method, ensemble with random forest method and tree with decision tree classifier. Additionally, splitting the train set and test set. To predicting the result by comparing accuracy.

Prediction result by accuracy: Logistic regression algorithm also uses a linear equation with independent predictors to predict a value. The predicted value can be anywhere between negative infinity to positive infinity. It needs the output of the algorithm to be classified variable data.

True Positive Rate (TPR) = $\text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN})$ False Positive rate (FPR) = $\text{FP} / (\text{FP} + \text{TN})$

Accuracy: The Proportion of the total number of predictions that is correct otherwise overall how often the model predicts correctly defaulters and non-defaulters.

Accuracy calculation = $(\text{TP} + \text{TN}) / (\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN})$

Accuracy is the most intuitive performance measure and it is simply a ratio of correctly predicted observation to the total observations. One may think that, if we have high accuracy then our model is best. Yes, accuracy is a great measure but only when you have symmetric datasets where values of false positive and false negatives are almost same.

Precision: Precision is the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positive observations. The question that this metric answer is of all passengers that labelled as survived, how many actually survived? High precision relates to the low false positive rate. We have got 0.788 precision which is pretty good.

Recall: Recall (Sensitivity) - Recall is the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the all observations in actual class - yes.

$$\text{Recall} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN})$$

Score: It is the weighted average of Precision and Recall. Therefore, this score takes both false positives and false negatives into account.

General Formula:

$$\text{F- Measure} = 2\text{TP} / (2\text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{FN})$$

F1-Score Formula:

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 * (\text{Recall} * \text{Precision}) / (\text{Recall} + \text{Precision})$$

Conclusion

- This application can help to find the human diabetes problems.
- The best accuracy o score is will be found out.
- Using these techniques there is less chance of error rate.

References

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